

Data Management

Web Panel Sample Service

Service Catalogue

Web Panel Sample Service (WPSS)

There is no shortage of existing web survey platforms. Generally, along with user-friendly questionnaire design tools, they allow users to manage lists of contacts to which surveys may be distributed through different communication channels. However, for the fielding of cross-national high quality surveys, major shortcomings remain. First, access to panelist data should be confined to local national coordinators, and while it needs to be kept up to date, probably not all of it is appropriate to be shared with a third-party survey platform. Second, survey orchestration should be handled centrally (at the so-called 'headquarter' level), but without detailed access to individual panelist data. Third, contact modes with panelists not only must include both email and SMS, but they should be possible to freely intertwine during fieldwork: for example, sending an email invite and an SMS reminder.

A review of existing survey platforms showed that none would meet these three constraints single-handedly. Hence the need for a dedicated sample management layer that, paired with a survey platform, makes a whole that is fit to meet the needs of cross-national and centrally orchestrated surveys. That is precisely the gap that WPSS tries to fill.

What is a Web Panel Sample Service?

The Web Panel Sample Service is a web application paired with the Qualtrics survey platform (with a tailored GDPR compliant license) to meet the specific needs (detailed above) of cross-national web surveys. WPSS enables centralised management of survey fielding orchestration (publishing, sending invites and reminders...) and decentralised and privacy-compliant handling of panelist data. Use cases can be found in the Social Sciences and Humanities (CRONOS-2 project) but may extend to broader contexts as well. A prototype of the WPSS has been developed and extensively tested in 2021 within 11 European countries. Starting October 2021, a new release of the WPSS will support its first full-scale use case, within the frame of ESS ERIC for its web panel spinoff of the ESS round 10 (funded under ESS-SUSTAIN-2).

Key features

- ➔ Multilingual support:
 - ➔ Panelist portals can be translated into the local language
 - ➔ All email, SMS and surveys are displayed in the panelist's preferred language
- ➔ Content editors drafting surveys, messages and translations thereof need not have access to WPSS and can be hired outside of the survey management team.

- ➔ Fieldwork orchestration actions (survey publishing, sending of invites and reminders...) are only accessible to users with headquarter privileges. However, headquarter users have no access to detailed panelist data.
- ➔ Users with National Coordinator privileges have access and are responsible for the accuracy of panelist data in the sample(s) they manage. This is made as little burdensome as possible by allowing panelists to edit a large part of their data themselves on their profile page.
- ➔ Email and SMS as contact mode, that can be freely intertwined
- ➔ Online user documentation is publicly available.

Benefits

- ➔ Whilst the tool is designed initially for the ESS, it is developed to maximise the chances that other large-scale cross-national survey infrastructures will want to use it in the longer term.
- ➔ WPSS can be used in various studies where managing a sample and distributing surveys in a multilingual context and in line with the GDPR regulation is needed, for the SSH and many other domains.
- ➔ Adoption by users is facilitated by an online wiki.
- ➔ The software has been, from the very start conceived and developed with high software quality standards (sustainable, easy to deploy).

More Information

- ➔ Report: [D4.1 A sample management system for cross-national web survey](#)
- ➔ Presentation: [Operating a Web Panel Sample Service \(WPSS\)](#)
- ➔ [WPSS online wiki](#)

Who made the tool

ESS ERIC HQ and Sciences Po, development: Sciences Po

[Access the WPSS on the SSHOC Service Catalogue](#)

[WPSS Instance in use by ESS-ERIC](#)

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"Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud", has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 project call H2020-INFRAEOSC-04-2018, grant agreement #823782

